

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF THIN TITANIUM FILMS / CFRP HYBRID LAMINATES CONTAINING TRANSITION REGION

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1 Introduction

Application of carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRPs), such for Boeing 787 aircraft, enable us to manufacture large scale structure in the form of single-piece and considerable reduction of number of components has been achieved. Mechanical fastening using bolt-nut or rivets, however, is necessary in the final assembly of aircraft fuselage etc. so far. On the one side mechanical fastening has an advantage in assembly and technicians can inspect inside the structure by easy disassembly, on the other hand, carbon fiber composite laminates are sensitive to stress concentration around such as an open circular hole or notch, and resulted in damage onset in relatively low stress. For composite bolted joints currently applied to aerospace structures, thicker composite plates are used locally around the joints in order to assure the safety. These facts spoil the lightweight characteristics of carbon fiber composites. In addition, complicated design is needed because thickness change in the plate causes singular stress state and secondary bending moment. In this regard, composite bolted joints which have high specific strength and better robustness are required. Fink *et al.* [1,2] have been trying to deal with this problem by applying the concept of Fiber-Metal Laminates (FMLs) [3] with titanium alloy inserted in the carbon fiber composites near the bolted joints. They evaluated the bearing strength and damage behavior in the hybrid laminates and showed some progressive damage analyses using finite element method. Authors also have been evaluating the application of the hybrid laminates

with relatively thin titanium films embedded in CFRPs to the bolted joints [4]. They have argued optimization of the hybrid stacking sequence based on the experimental obtained bearing strength and damage behavior, with a concept that the titanium films prevent the matrix cracking in the CFRPs induced by the fiber kinking in adjacent 0° ply under bearing loading to grow. The hybrid plate is deemed to be not applied to the whole structure but local region near stress concentrations such as the bolted joints since the usage of the hybrid plate results in gain in weight because of high density of metal. In this situation there should be "transition region", so Fink *et al.* called, where metal volume fraction gradually decreased with the distance from the bolt-hole. However, there are few papers available that deal with the effect of the transition region on the mechanical properties of the hybrid laminates. In this paper, the transition region in the Fiber-Metal laminates that consist of carbon fibers and pure titanium films is of interest. Strength and damage behavior of the hybrid laminates with the transition region under tensile or bending loading are investigated. The optimization in the configuration of the transition region is discussed based on the experimentally obtained results.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

The hybrid laminates were assembled by laminating carbon fiber/epoxy prepregs (T700SC/2592, Toray) and pure titanium films (50µm in thickness, Sumitomo Metals Naetsu Works), and cured in an autoclave. Since one of the drawbacks in this kind of

hybrid laminates is the adhesion between two materials, surface pretreatment is often applied to the titanium. A sol-gel treatment is sometimes applied as reported in Ref. [5] though it is an expensive method. Based on the report in dental materials area [6], the titanium films here were soaked in hydrogen peroxide solution of 30% for 1 hour before the lamination to improve their adhesion to epoxy resin.

2.2 Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) and End Notched Flexure (ENF) Tests

In order to evaluate the quality of the interlaminar adhesion between the titanium films and epoxy, DCB and ENF tests were conducted based on the JIS K7086. The titanium film was inserted in between 12th and 13th ply in a unidirectional laminates $[0]_{24}$, and a demold sheet was also inserted in one side of the titanium/CFRP interface to introduce an initial notch. The tests were conducted using the specimen with or without surface treated titanium films, and the unidirectional CFRP laminates were also used for the comparison. Interlaminar fracture toughness in mode I and II at initial crack growth G_{IC} and G_{IIC} were obtained from the DCB and ENF tests.

2.3 Tensile and Bending Tests for the Hybrid Laminates containing the Transition Region

Mechanical properties of the hybrid laminate containing the transition region were obtained by tensile and four-point bending tests. We prepared the FML containing four pattern of transition region as shown in Fig.1. As shown in Table 1 the stacking sequences of the FML specimen are combination of a quasi-isotropic carbon fiber composite laminates $[45/0/-45/90]_{2s}$ and five titanium films inserted in the CFRP laminates, and three types of the stacking sequences were applied as the specimen. Here, the specimen type is denoted by using stacking sequence type and the transition region pattern, for example, FML-A-1 stands for the stacking type A and the transition pattern 1. The quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates and the hybrid laminates without the transition region, denoted by transition pattern 0, were also used for comparison. Tensile tests were conducted by Tensilon universal testing machine (RTF-1350, A&D) under cross-head speed of 1.0 mm/min. Another universal testing machine (SC-5H, JT TOHSI) was used for the four-point bending tests. The cross-head speed was 3.0 mm/min. The support

and the loading span were 100 mm and 40 mm respectively, and the specimen was set on the support so as the middle of the transition region to be at the center of the testing jig as shown in Fig.2.

Fig.1 Four patterns for the transition region. (Hybrid stacking sequence in this figure is type A.)

Table 1 Stacking sequence of the CFRP and hybrid laminates.

Specimen	Stacking sequence	Areal density [g/cm ²]
CFRP	$[45/0/-45/90]_{2s}$	0.35
FML-A	$[45/0/-45/Ti/90/45/0/Ti/-45/90/Ti/90/-45/Ti/0/45/90/Ti/-45/0/45]$	0.46
FML-B	$[45/Ti/0/Ti/-45/90/45/0/-45/90/Ti/90/-45/0/45/90/-45/Ti/0/Ti/45]$	
FML-C	$[45/0/-45/90/45/Ti/0/Ti/-45/90/Ti/90/-45/Ti/0/Ti/45/90/-45/0/45]$	

Fig.2 4 Point bending test setup.

Fig.3 Load-COD curve for DCB tests.

Fig.4 Load-Displacement curve for ENF tests.

Table 2 Mode I and II fracture toughness.

	G_{IC} [J/m ²]	G_{IIC} [J/m ²]
Non-treated	35	422
Pretreated	75	950
CFRP	331	1137

3 Results and discussion

3.1 DCB and ENF test results

The load-COD (crack-tip opening displacement) curves and the load-displacement curves obtained by the DCB and ENF testing are shown in Fig.3 and Fig.4 respectively, and the interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IC} and G_{IIC} were averaged in Table 2. By the easy surface treatment using hydrogen peroxide solution these values almost double compared to that without the surface treatment for the titanium film, and approached the value for the CFRP, especially

Fig.5 Fracture surface of the DCB test specimen.

Fig.6 Fracture surface of the ENF test specimen.

in G_{IIC} . These improvements are considered to be due to the anchor effect by the epoxy resin that intrudes asperity of the titanium surface introduced by the treatment. Fig.5 and Fig.6 shows fracture surfaces after DCB and ENF tests respectively observed by SEM. One can see that epoxy resin did not remain at the titanium surface that kept smooth without the treatment. On the other hand, the resin can be seen on the pretreated titanium. These facts also explain the increase of the interlaminar fracture toughness.

Fig.7 Tensile strength and bending strength for the CFRP laminates and the thin titanium/CFRP fiber-metal laminates.

Fig.8 Stress-strain curves for FML-A with different transition regions, and FML-B-2 and C-2.

Fig.9 Initial damages in FML containing the transition region under stress of 300MPa.

3.2 Tensile and Bending Loading on the Hybrid Laminates containing the Transition Region

Obtained tensile and bending strength were shown in Fig.7. It should be noted that plate thickness of the hybrid laminates containing the transition region slightly decreases from hybrid part to CFRP part. Both tensile strength and bending strength were calculated using the cross-section area in the hybrid part. As the pattern 0 specimen which is hybrid laminates without the transition region showed lower tensile strength compared to the CFRP laminates, this is a convincing result because the

strength of titanium film itself is about 290MPa that is much lower than the strength of quasi-isotropic carbon fiber composite laminates of about 840MPa. Among hybrid laminates containing transition region, only FML-A series were influenced by transition region pattern under tensile loading. In FML-A series, FML-A-2 and FML-A-3 indicated higher tensile strength than the rest. Although no significant effects on the tensile strength were achieved by the transition region pattern in FML-B and FML-C series, these specimens showed a higher strength than FML-A series. Fig.8 shows stress-strain curves for the FML-A series, FML-B-2 and FML-C-2. Here,

strain was obtained by strain gage attached on the surface above the middle of the transition region. One can see that each behavior is almost the same, however, FML-A-2 showed higher fracture strain in the FML-A series. In addition, the fracture strain for FML-B-2 and FML-C-2 were also higher than that of FML-A series. The strain for the FML-B-2 and FML-C-2 were increased rapidly just before the fracture. It is considered that the differences in the stacking sequences of the hybrid laminates specimen result in the variation in the strain behavior and the tensile strength obtained. As shown in Fig.9, Among for all transition region patterns and all stacking sequences, crack in 90° layer and transverse cracking occurred as initial damage at the edge of the titanium film that inserted in the through-thickness center of the laminate (i.e., between 90° plies) under stress of about 300MPa, and interfacial delamination between titanium film and 90° ply occurred at almost the same time. Then, the crack in 90° layer which occurred at the edge of the titanium film propagated through the 90° ply in the loading direction, and transverse crack occurred at the 90° ply propagated into the 45° ply in through thickness direction as shown in Fig.10. Fig.11 shows damages near the edge of the titanium films in FML-A-1 under stress of 660MPa. For pattern 1 where the titanium edges aligned on a line, matrix cracking at the edge of the titanium film that inserted in the through-thickness center of the laminate was connected to other cracks initiated from the edge of adjacent titanium films. As a result, FML-A-1 ruptured at the edge of the titanium films, on the other hand pattern 2 and 3 specimen tend to rupture in the CFRP part as shown in Fig.12. This is the reason that FML-A-1 showed lower strength than the rest. Next, we considered the effect of stacking sequence on the damage behavior and the tensile strength. As shown in Fig.13, on the one side cracks at the edge of the titanium film in 90° layer were also observed near the titanium edge which is not at the center in FML-A, on the other hand, in FML-B and FML-C damages of CFRP part were suppressed because cracks in 90° layer occurred at the edge of the titanium film were not observed near the titanium edge. This is the one reason that series of FML-B and FML-C showed higher strength than FML-A series. Fig.14 shows damage appearance of hybrid part in FML-A, FML-B and FML-C.

Fig.10 Damages in 90° plies near the edge of the titanium film in FML-C-2 under stress of 730 MPa

Fig.11 Damages near the edge of the titanium film in FML-A-1 under stress of 660MPa

Fig.12 Damages after tensile test.

In FML-A-1, the 90° ply – titanium interfacial delamination was found to occur at not only the center but also other interfaces (Fig.14 (a)). It is interesting to note that the interfacial delamination could not be seen except for the center of plate for FML-B-3 and FML-C-2, this may be because there are no 90° ply- titanium interfaces (Fig.14 (b) and (c)). It is possible to prevent delamination by inserting titanium films in adjacent with the 0° plies, then as a result, tensile strength of FML-B, FML-C could be improved.

Next, we considered the effects of stacking sequences and transition region patterns on the 4 point bending strength. As shown in Fig.7, among hybrid laminates containing transition region, FML-B and FML-C series were influenced by transition region pattern and pattern 2 and pattern3 indicated higher bending strength than the rest. On the other hand, no significant effects on the bending strength can be seen for the transition region pattern in FML-A series. Among all transition region patterns, FML-B series showed a lower bending strength than FML-A and FML-C series. Load-displacement curves for FML-A-3, FML-B-3 and FML-C-3 under 4 point bending tests shown together in Fig.15, here displacement indicates that of the cross-head of the testing machine. FML-B-3 showed gradual load increase until about 17mm of displacement. Then, it

ruptured when the bending load reached the maximum. In FML-A-3 and FML-C-3, bending load was gradually decreased after the load reached the maximum then ruptured. Displacement at fracture of FML-A-3 and FML-C-3 were about 21mm and 25mm respectively, and it was larger than FML-B-3. Fig.16 showed damages after four point bending test for FML-A-3, FML-B-3 and FML-C-3.

(a) FML-A-1 (660MPa) (b) FML-B-2 (720MPa) (c) FML-C-2 (720MPa)
 Fig.14 Delamination at Ti-90° interface in hybrid region.

Fig.13 Damages near the edge of the titanium film under stress of 730MPa

Fig.15 Load-Displacement curves for FML-A-4, FML-B-4 and FML-C-4.

In this figure upper half of the laminates receive compression by bending. The buckling tends to be occurred at the edge of titanium films inserted near the outermost layer in FML-B-3 (Fig.16 (b)). Titanium films inserted near the outermost layer are found to let the bending strength low since the buckling occurred at small displacements. In FML-A-3 and FML-C-3, no buckling occurred at the edge of titanium films and these specimen bear to large load.

3.3 Conclusions

The effect of stacking sequence and configuration in the transition region, as a result of hybrid laminates with locally inserted titanium films around the stress concentration were evaluated by the tensile and four-point bending tests. As for the tensile strength, only FML-A series were influenced by transition region pattern. In FML-A series, the highest combination of tensile strength was found to be achieved for the stacking sequence where inner 0° plies were sandwiched by the titanium films and for the transition region that had staggered edge of the titanium films. Although no significant effects on

the tensile strength were found among the transition region patterns in FML-B and FML-C series, these specimens showed a higher strength than FML-A series because damages of CFRP part in FML-B and FML-C series were suppressed. The suppression of the matrix cracking in 90° plies by the titanium films and the interfacial delamination between the films and carbon fiber plies except for 90° plies are considered to result in the high strength.

As for the bending strength, FML-A and FML-C series indicated higher bending strength than FML-B series because the buckling was occurred at the edge of titanium films that inserted near the outermost layer under small displacements in FML-B series. From what has been discussed above, FML-C-2 shows the good property in both tensile and bending tests.

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Fig.16 Damages after four point bending test.

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